

Goal: To provide wildlife connectivity data to support decisions on the most efficient areas for conservation action in a landscape in Ghana threatened by multiple socio-economic changes.

- Natural forest
- Disturbed forest
- Cocoa + trees
- Cocoa
- Open
- Developed
- Water

Fig. 1 Cocoa farming landscape between Krokosua Hills Forest Reserve (east) & Bia National Park (west)*.

CONDATIS PARAMETERS

What kind of species are we interested in?	Forest-associated species of moderate specialism (able to use shade cocoa). Habitat quality is defined by tree cover (TS1) or by overall species richness (TS2).
What is our source and target?	Source is Krokosua Hills ; target is Bia National Park
Why do our species need to move?	Habitat fragmentation (& climate change)
What constitutes habitat?	Shade cocoa (Cocoa + trees) & forest (Natural & Disturbed)*
What kind of prioritisation are we performing?	Identification of key locations for restoration of cocoa agroforestry /expansion of shade cocoa
Who will be interested in the results?	National REDD+ Secretariat, Forestry Commission

*Land cover data provided by David Hughell (see Rainforest Alliance (2014). *Nature Ecosystem Assessment Baseline for Ghana and Indonesia*. Evaluation and Research Program, Rainforest Alliance.

SUMMARY CONDATIS RESULTS

- Low flow
- Medium flow
- High flow

The main flow pathways are shown in the southern part of the landscape between Krokosua and Bia, and along networks of proximate forest patches.

Fig. 2 Example flow map, for TS1, with a dispersal distance of 0.2km, reproductive rate of 1000 individuals/km² and habitat of Natural forest + Disturbed forest + Cocoa + trees; the source and target are 1km strips of forest at the edge of each protected area (transparent).

Restoring cocoa agroforestry could be beneficial over large portions of this landscape, but especially in the south and in 'buffer zones' at the edge of each protected area.

- Low dropping rank
- Medium dropping rank
- High dropping rank

Fig. 4 For each theoretical species (TS1 and 2) in this landscape, for each dispersal distance, the overall speed is high, i.e. this is a well connected landscape.

Fig. 3 Example of prioritising cells where *Sun Cocoa* could be restored to cocoa agroforestry (i.e. *Cocoa + trees*); Colours represent the **dropping rank – when this is high, restoration leads to a steeper increase in speed of movement.** Analysis shown for TS2, with a dispersal distance of 1km, reproductive rate of 1000 individuals/km², habitat and source/target as in Fig. 2, and habitat cells have been dropped over 50 stages using flow-based dropping.